

Research Article

Psychopathology of the Syndrome Grouping Hyperactivity, Anxiety, Self-Mutilation, Borderline Personality, Refractory Depression, High Propensity for Suicide. Role of Mirror Neurons and Hormonal and Catecholaminergic Dysregulation in Pathophysiology

Luiz Costa¹, Samuel Ribeiro¹, Daniela Murta¹, Pedro Tavares¹, Vívian Pereira¹, Álvaro Vieira¹, Josimar Silva¹, Aderrone Mendes¹, Valéria Borges¹, Janaina de Faria¹, Ester Borges¹, Dalva Medeiros¹, Isabela Sarmento¹, Danilo Guerra¹, Paula Paiva¹, Marcelo Caixeta^{1*}

1. Research Psychiatrist, Federal University of Goiás – Brazil.

How to cite this article: L. Costa, S. Ribeiro, D. Murta, P. Tavares, V. Pereira, et al. (2025). Psychopathology of the Syndrome Grouping Hyperactivity, Anxiety, Self-Mutilation, Borderline Personality, Refractory Depression, High Propensity for Suicide. Role of Mirror Neurons and Hormonal and Catecholaminergic Dysregulation in Pathophysiology, International Journal of Psychiatric Practice, RPC Publishers, 1(1); DOI: <https://www.doi.org/rpc/2025/rpc.ijpp/00382>

Copyright license: © 2025 Marcelo Caixeta, this is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

***Address for correspondence:** Marcelo Caixeta, Research Psychiatrist, Federal University of Goiás – Brazil.

Email: psychological.medicine1@gmail.com

Submitted: July 15, 2025

Approved: August 14, 2025

Published: August 20, 2025

Abstract

In the present article, we resume the discussion on the shared pathophysiology among hyperactivity, autism, and dopaminergic dependence. We present an integrative overview of mirror neuron deficits, egocentric hyperendophasia, and the impacts of dopamine on anxiety, self-mutilation, and suicide attempts.

Keywords: hyperactivity; anxiety; self-mutilation; borderline personality; refractory depression; suicide; mirror neuron; hormonal dysregulation; catecholaminergic dysregulation; dopamine deficiency; hyperendophasia; general psychiatric syndrome

Introduction

In our article on the General Psychiatric Syndrome [1], we already discussed how several diseases share the same pathophysiology. Thus, we note that many hyperactive individuals, as well as autistic individuals-including because hyperactivity and autism are very closely linked-share characteristics. There are hyperactive autistic individuals and autistic hyperactive individuals.

Methods

This article is based on a clinical hypothesis developed from 45 years of continuous, intensive, and uninterrupted psychiatric practice, conducted within the context of a referral psychiatric hospital located in the Central-West region of Brazil. The institution in question treats patients with severe and refractory mental conditions, coming from various states of the federation, thus establishing itself as a regional clinical hub of high complexity. The formulation of the hypotheses presented results from an integration of the authors' direct experience with thousands of clinical cases and in-depth study of national and international scientific literature. The adopted approach is simultaneously psychopharmacological and psychotherapeutic, articulating concepts from dynamic psychiatry, neurobiology of mental disorders, and prolonged clinical observations of evolution and therapeutic response. The analysis was conducted qualitatively and exploratorily, through the systematization of recurrent psychopathological patterns, with special emphasis on conditions involving hyperactivity, impulsivity, self-mutilation, borderline behaviours, alterations in the dopaminergic system, and mirror neuron dysfunctions. Throughout this process, the authors developed explanatory clinical models aiming to understand the mechanisms underlying the symptomatology of these patients, their pathways of worsening, and possibilities for integrative management. This method falls within the field of phenomenological and comprehensive clinical investigation, typical of observational medical sciences, seeking to extract robust hypotheses from the confluence between specialized medical practice and accumulated theoretical references.

Results

We begin this section with some general clinical observations of a psychopathological nature. Many hyperactive autistic individuals have problems related to mirror neuron dysfunction. Many hyperactive individuals, even without being autistic, have a problem with mirror neurons. And this problem with mirror neurons affects not only their relationship with other people in childhood (mother-baby relationship) but also their view of the external world. So, they are somewhat closed off from the external world. They don't "enjoy" the external world. The external world doesn't enter them. They don't relax, they don't Savor the external world-like looking at a tree, looking at a bird, sitting on a chair outside the house, eating a cheese bread, drinking coffee sitting on the sidewalk at home, in a plastic chair. This patient doesn't enjoy the world. They are very much themselves. It's a lot of their own energy. They are very energetic, egocentric. This makes them hyperendophasic, looking too much into themselves. And besides, there's boredom, because they get tired quickly of working, studying. That doesn't feed them because of the insufficiency of pleasure; it doesn't give them enough dopamine. It's a dopamine deficiency syndrome [4-6]. At the same time, they have a lot of internal energy. And this internal energy has nowhere to go. In adolescents, for example, who cannot fully exercise their sexuality, this goes into masturbatory equivalents. For example, self-mutilation—which is a type of sexual masochism. So, they become very self-centred. They become "hyper-endogenized." They are not passively affected by the external world. They don't calm down. The external world doesn't calm them down, because their energy is too strong and needs to be exercised. This energy has nowhere to flow, and this generates agony, it generates anxiety. If the patient does not learn to relax, does not learn to work, does not learn to study, does not learn to channel this energy for the good of others-to do charity-this energy stays within them and generates anxiety. Often, the only recourse, in the face of successive disruptions, is to administer neuroleptics to the patient. But then it sedates the patient. The patient becomes "vegetative." Either it sedates or tranquilizes the patient, the patient becomes "vegetative." Then comes that "vegetation" syndrome. The patient who was already hyperactive before, who liked the carousel life, the adrenaline life, feels paradise lost ("before my life was much better, now I have no pleasure in anything, I'm a blank slate, I'm vegetative, I can't live like this"). So, this creates a complicated problem for clinical management. These patients also have a great affective craving, an eagerness, a very intense affective need. That's why they will become borderlines in the future, especially when they don't have a very nurturing mother, a mother who cuddles a lot, who gives a lot of support. Their mother doesn't calm them down. And then this internal energy becomes even stronger due to the lack of this nurturing mother, the lack of this "calming" mother. If he does not receive this maternal care from the mother—either because his mirror neuron is poor, or because the mother is poor, or because his craving is too great—he also cannot calm himself. It doesn't calm his internal elements. The external world does not penetrate him, does not make him passive. He remains very active, with a very active ego, without the passivation of the world. These patients have a low degree of passivity towards the world. They don't relax with the world. Others also don't enter them. This is because of the mirror neuron problem [2,3]. They have a very strong ego. The world doesn't enter them. The world sometimes enters as an annoyance. Then comes the relative autism side that many also have: not tolerating much noise, not tolerating the world. The world bothers them, it's annoying. They don't like many people. Anywhere they are, in the case of the hyperactive person, they need to be the protagonists. For example, at a bar table, they cannot stay silent for long. They have to be the center of attention. They cannot be spectators. They don't occupy themselves with others, with other people. They don't look at others; they only occupy themselves with themselves. They don't calm down with others, they don't calm down with the world. This generates consequences. Because he was hyperactive in childhood, and then in youth he will become anxious. And from anxious, he becomes depressive. And from depressive, suicidal. So, this explains the pathophysiology of many refractory suicidal patients. In some clinical configurations, self-mutilators, sexual masochists, and borderlines fall within this psychopathology. These patients are difficult to treat because they need psychotherapy that makes them open up to the world, makes them relax, takes them out of egocentrism, and leads them to some useful activity to escape boredom and hyperendophasia. Because they also don't like anything that normal people like: watching television, watching a movie, reading a book, talking, taking a walk, having that calm of being with their child. None of this appeases them. Having a steady job also doesn't appease them. So, they remain in that agony. And from this agony, the problems are increased. All these problems, in adolescence, tend to worsen with hormones. What was hyperactivity transforms into a mood disorder. Through hormones—which affect cortisol, gonadal hormones—the patient becomes more worried, more anxious, more aggressive, because they tend to dominate the territory. The hormone prepares it for adult life. Then comes the worry. Obsessions come. And all of this becomes depressive, because this more intense anxiety also exhausts the patient. And intense anxiety turns into obsession. And this obsession, within depression, turns into an obsession with suicide [4,6].

Discussion

Mirror Neurons and Isolation from the External World: Hyperactive, autistic, or comorbid patients often exhibit mirror neuron system dysfunction [2,3,7], compromising empathy and social interaction.

Hyperendophasia, Boredom, and Dopaminergic Dependence Syndrome: These individuals exhibit intense internal energy and hyperendophasia-exacerbated self-focus in addition to quickly experiencing boredom in routine activities. This condition is based on a dopamine deficiency syndrome [4-6].

Adolescence: Self-Mutilation and Sexual Masochism: When deprived of expressing sexuality, hyperactive adolescents direct their energy toward self-mutilation and masochistic behaviours, aggravated by the absence of emotional support.

Treatment with Neuroleptics and a Sense of “Paradise Lost”: Neuroleptic use may help but frequently results in emotional flattening.

Affective Craving and Borderline Tendency: The lack of emotional containment fosters borderline tendencies.

Clinical Evolution: The trajectory typically progresses from hyperactivity → anxiety → depression → suicidal behaviour [1,4,6].

Conclusion

The interaction between mirror neuron dysfunction and dopaminergic deficiency underlies a condition that evolves from hyperactivity and hyperendophasia to anxiety, depression, and suicidal risk. The approach should be multidisciplinary, involving psychotherapy, emotional support, and judicious use of medication.

References

1. Caixeta M. (2025). General Psychiatric Syndrome: A New Perspective on the Theory of Unitary Psychosis. *J Psychiatry Ment Disord*, 10(1):1083.
2. Oberman LM. (2005). EEG evidence for mirror neuron dysfunction in autism spectrum disorders. *Cogn Brain Res*, 24(2):190-198.
3. Dapretto M. (2006). Understanding emotions in others: mirror neuron dysfunction in children with autism. *Nat Neurosci*, 9(1):28-30.
4. Dum R. (2022). Dopamine receptor expression and the pathogenesis of ADHD. *Curr Dev Disord Rep*, 9(4):127-136.
5. Volkow ND. (2009). Imaging dopamine reward pathway in ADHD. *JAMA*, 302(10):1084-1091.
6. Blum K. (2004). Dopamine dysregulation syndrome: an overview. *Curr Opin Neurol*, 17(6):681-687.
7. Hamilton AFdeC. (2013). Reflecting on the mirror neuron system in autism. *Dev Cogn Neurosci*, 3:91-105.
8. Spencer TJ. (2011). Striatal dopamine transporter alterations in ADHD. *Am J Psychiatry*, 168(1):101-110.
9. Ramachandran VS, Oberman LM. (2006). Broken Mirrors: a theory of autism. *Sci Am*, 295(5):62-67.
10. Pineda JA. (2005). The functional significance of mu rhythms. *Brain Res Rev*, 50(1):57-68.
11. Hallowell E, Ratey J. (2021). *ADHD 2.0: New Science*. New York: Ballantine.
12. Caixeta M. (2025). Mirror-neurons and psychiatric regulation. Zenodo/OSF.